

INFLUENCE OF GENDER MAINSTREAMING ON PERFORMANCE OF CONSTITUENCY DEVELOPMENT FUNDED PROJECTS IN KACHELIBA CONSTITUENCY, WEST POKOT COUNTY, KENYA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7327478>

Published Date: 16-November-2022

Abstract: Gender mainstreaming has become an issue of major concern in implementation of development projects around the world. However, several challenges have emerged on how to implement gender mainstreaming especially in government projects and in non-governmental organizations. The reasons alluded to for not implementing gender mainstreaming programs consist of lack of resources and awareness that can promote gender mainstreaming awareness campaigns. In other cases, there is lack of clear policies that can guide the gender mainstreaming process. Among, the most affected projects include the constituency development fund where majority of the people appointed to lead the committee are mostly men. In cases, where women are represented, they are always underrepresented and this affects their participation in decision making especially where voting is expected. This study therefore sought to address the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects in Kenya: a case of Kacheliba Constituency. The specific objectives of the study were: to examine the influence of gender policy on the performance of CDF projects in Kacheliba Constituency, to examine the influence of cultural practices on performance of constituency development fund of Kacheliba Constituency, to find out the influence of availability of gender mainstreaming resources on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency and to assess the influence of gender awareness on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency. The study utilized a descriptive research design. The target populations of this study were 200 respondents comprising of CDF committee members, Project leaders, Community members, and project leaders. The sample size of 398 respondents was determined through purposive sampling. In pilot study, Thirty nine (39) questionnaires were distributed to targeted respondents in Kacheliba Constituency, West Pokot County involving respondents that did not take part in the actual study. Out of the total number of questionnaires distributed, twenty nine (29) questionnaires were satisfactorily filled and returned, eight (8) was incomplete and therefore considered not satisfactory for the purpose of the study, while two of the questionnaire was not returned at all. This represented a response rate of 74.36% which was considered convenient and hence acceptable for data analysis. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2013), a response rate above 70% is well recommended for research purposes. The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between gender policy and the performance of CDF projects. The study results also showed that cultural practices have no significant effect on the performance of CDF projects based on $\beta_2 = 0.073$ (p-value = 0.061 which is greater than $\alpha = 0.05$). The study further concluded that a significant relationship exists between the gender mainstreaming resources and the performance of CDF projects, the effect of the gender mainstreaming resources was expressed by the value of the test $t = 1.876$ which implies that the standard error associated with the parameter is greater than the effect of the parameter. The study concluded that gender awareness had a positive and significant effect on the performance of

CDF projects based on $\beta_4 = 0.327$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$). This study therefore recommends that gender issues should be properly articulated to be implemented. The study recommends that equal opportunity to participate in decision making should accord to both men and women. The study recommends that the constituency must ensure the gender mainstreaming issues programs are put in place to address gender issues. The study recommends that another study be conducted on influence of gender mainstreaming in the county governments projects in Kenya. Additionally, a replication study must be conducted in another county for there to be sufficient and conclusive results regarding the study.

Keywords: Gender policy, cultural practices, performance of CDF Projects and gender awareness.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background of the study

According to Wallby (2004), gender mainstreaming refers to the practice of incorporating gender equality issues in the decision making and policy making process through making explicit natural gendered outcomes and assumptions. In other words, gender mainstreaming is a procedure that ensures equal opportunity is provided to both women and men (Nyawira, 2011). According to Gatimu (2015) the Beijing Conference that was held in 1995 by the United Nations established gender mainstreaming as a global strategy. The role of this conference was educating the entire world on the importance of gender equality in accessing career opportunities and education for both women and men. For Monjane (2015) gender mainstreaming is responsible in making sure both women and men have equal opportunities in the country's development process and in the energy sector. Additionally, gender plays a critical role in promoting economic development and growth (Mikolla, 2007).

According to Mikolla (2007), gender plays a significant role in economic development and growth; she further notes that market technologies have changed the role of women in economic outputs while changing the old gender hierarchical valuations in the society. However, her findings indicate that women in overall have fewer economic opportunities, although countries where women have access to economic opportunities are more affluent economically. Ryan (2007) study on gender mainstreaming and empowerment, indicate that the role of women in social and political contexts has been on the rise and has been constantly recognized in the last decade. According to FAO (2016) gender mainstreaming is the process of assessing the implications for women and men of any planned action, including legislation, policies or programmes, in all areas and at all levels. It is a strategy for making women's as well as men's concerns and experiences an integral dimension of the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of policies and programmes in all political, economic and societal spheres so that women and men benefit equally and inequality is not perpetuated. The ultimate goal is to achieve gender equality'. When necessary, the mainstreaming approach can be complemented by specific women-targeted / gender-equality interventions and action, especially in the areas where significant gender-based discrimination persist.

Global perspective of Gender Mainstreaming

Globally, the contribution of women in the agricultural sector and economic development has not been very robust especially in Africa (FAO, (2003). It is estimated that Asian countries have higher numbers of women who contribute to economic development specifically in the agriculture sector. For instance, Bangladesh, China, Vietnam, Pakistan, India and Cambodia have between 60 to 98 percent of women who are employed in the agricultural sector. According to World Bank (2017) women's role in family management, decision making and access to and control of household's resources is still very limited. Subsequently, the role of women as housewives subjects them to inadequate skill jobs which do not allow them to get employment in sectors that can provide them with a good pay Seattle and Cohen (2017).

According to (Metle (2002) in Kuwait the number of women has improved but is still far from achieving equality, especially equality in advancement, even if women are hired for offices in public and private administration with equal pay none of them have decision-making positions with respect to their male counterparts. Subsequently, Kuwait women are not allowed to hold key positions of power in the government sector. The study also established that there is a widespread belief that men should take precedence over women. This means that men should have a higher priority than women.

The study conducted in Oman and Bahrain of women in management positions (Wikinson, 2006) showed that the main challenges faced by women are cultural taboos, discrimination at work, lack of trust in female managers and negative attitudes towards women. In another study, Jamali et al, (2005) on the limitations faced by women's taboos in Lebanon indicated that the main challenge women face in career advancement stems from cultural expectations and patriarchal

attitudes that emphasize the role of women as housewives and mothers. This means that even if women aspire to advance in their careers, they cannot because their primary role simply revolves around the family.

Regional perspective of Gender mainstreaming

In the African context, the role of women in participating in economic development remains low. For instance, women face challenges in controlling and accessing resources. The most affected population is rural women who are deprived access to ownership of resources, decent jobs, and participation in decision making. Nonetheless, women form the large share of workforce in the agricultural sector in sub-Saharan Africa which is estimated around 30 and 80% (UN, 2019).

According to World Bank (2014) African women are considered by men to be less productive. This makes the contribution of women less visible in the agricultural sector. Additionally, gender inequalities prevent women's access and control over productive and financial resources that are very crucial in promoting women's well-being. The result of isolation of women involvement in productive resources limits their productivity in agriculture, which can lead to food insecurity (UN, 2019).

According to Omwolo (2020) the participation of women in development projects is not very robust in Africa as compared to other countries globally. The result of these low levels of women participation emanates largely from discriminatory views on the position and role of women in the society. Women are always given lower positions than men which lead to unequal power relations between women and men. For Kongolo and Bamgose (2002) discriminatory views over women tend to legitimize and in some instances contribute to gender based violence which hinders women unable to participate effectively in development projects such CDF projects.

Furthermore, these harmful and discriminatory practices frequently prevent women from accomplishing their full potential and from playing their roles as productive members of society for the reason that they lead in unequal access to education, health care, economic opportunity, and participation in government and politics. Even in countries where women play a larger role in development, governance and politics, such as Kenya, women are treated and judged unequally and harshly by both institutions and by the public in comparison with their male counterparts (Matiku, 2013).

Local perspective of Gender mainstreaming

In Kenya, the issue of gender mainstreaming has not been fully implemented especially in the government sectors. The level of women participation in Development projects such as CDF projects remains to be low. In most cases, men often dominate in the leadership positions of the constituency development funded projects. This makes women unable to participate effectively in decision making regarding the implementation of CDF projects.

In many spheres, gender mainstreaming has not been handled seriously. For instance, the study that was conducted by Gatimu,(2015) on the challenges facing gender mainstreaming in Kenya prisons, indicated that gender mainstreaming in Kenyan prisons is not effective due to lack of adequate funding for training and implementing human resource policies. The researcher suggests adequate and timely approval of budgets and finances allocated to sensitization of gender equality awareness.

Mwenda, (2012) studied gender mainstreaming in the upgrade of Karatina market in Kenya. Findings from the study indicate that project managers were aware of gender mainstreaming policies put in place by the government of Kenya. The researcher reveals factors that hinder gender-mainstreaming policies for example: existence of cultural barriers and discriminatory attitudes from men who consider construction as a male oriented field.

Statement of the problem

Incorporating gender mainstreaming in development projects such as CDF projects remains a major challenge in most countries in Africa, Kenya included. Accordingly, women participation in the management, decision making and implementation of the CDF projects is predominantly dominated by men. In few cases, women are given the positions to chair the CDF committees. According to the County integrated Development Plans of Trans Nzoia County 2018-2022, gender inequality is a critical challenge that must be addressed to prevent women from being confined in domestic chores to get involved in decision making committees such as the CDF committee. Though many organizations recognize gender equality as a major ingredient in promoting economic development and in leading to gender balance and bring equal development, its implementation has always been underscored (Vera et al, 2018). Accordingly, changing gender roles plays a crucial role in the economic development of modern societies. Empirical evidence suggests that low productivity levels

are also linked to discriminative gender structures. In most parts of Kenya including Kacheliba Constituency, women are traditionally responsible for staple crop production, while often facing obstacles to access productive assets and to participate in economic development (Andersson-Djurfeldt et al. 2013). According to World Bank (2007) estimates, this fact reduces the productivity of women at an average rate of 22% hence a hindrance to economic growth and development. The studies aforementioned focused on gender mainstreaming in non-governmental organizations and few government funded projects and none of the studies focused on gender mainstreaming in CDF projects in Kenya. It is in view of the gaps in gender mainstreaming in development projects that this study sought to study the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects in Kenya: a case of Kacheliba Constituency.

Objectives of the study

General objective of the study

The general objective of this study was to examine the influence of gender mainstreaming on performance of CDF projects in Kenya: a case of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency.

Specific objectives of the study

The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To assess the influence of gender policy on performance of constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency.
2. To examine the influence of cultural practices on performance of constituency development fund of Kacheliba Constituency.
3. To determine the influence of availability of gender mainstreaming resources on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency.
4. To find out the influence of gender awareness on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency.

Research questions

1. What is the influence of gender policy on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency?
2. What is the influence of cultural practices on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency?
3. What is the influence of availability of gender mainstreaming resources on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency?
4. What is the influence of gender awareness on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency?

Significance of the study

The study findings will be valuable to all stakeholders working in Kacheliba Constituency and Kenya at large. It is hoped that it will provide relevant information that can guide organizations, national and county governments, CDF committee, community and other stakeholders in gender sector to employ favorable interventions, policy and practice to support women participation in development work.

Significance of the study to national and county government

The outcome of the study will be used by the national and county government in allocation of resources pertaining to involvement of gender mainstreaming in implementation of the project. The study also will help the county assembly to expedite legislation of policies and framework that will create conducive environment for both gender to participate in development work.

Significance of the study to local and international development organization.

The study will also be used by local and international development organizations in designing and implementation of community projects while considering gender perspective.

Significance of the study to the local community

The whole local societies could use the results of this study to transform their approach towards gender mainstreaming and the part it plays in improvement of development projects. The men in communities will see the necessity of integrating women in development projects and therefore advance the living standard of the community.

Scope of the study

The scope of the study is to investigate the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of development projects in Kenya: a case of CDF projects of Kacheliba Constituency with specific objectives of establishing the influence of gender policy on performance the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency, examining the influence of cultural practices on performance of constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency, and assessing the influence of gender awareness on performance of the constituency development funded projects of Kacheliba Constituency.

Limitation of the study

The limitation of the study was in the cost incurred due to the vastness of the area which required significant amount of time to collect adequate data, which the study had no control over. To overcome this limitation, the researcher contracted a research assistant. This ensured that the targeted population was reached.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW**Introduction:**

This chapter will discuss the existing literature on gender mainstreaming. It includes the theoretical framework guiding the study, determinants of gender mainstreaming, empirical review and the summary of the chapter.

Theoretical Review

This section provides the theories and approaches that will guide this study which are: Model of public policy making, Butler's Gender Relations Theory, Women in Development Approach and Resource based-value theory.

Model of public political opinions

Models of Public policy is taken into account to be relevant in understanding the influence of gender policy on performance of CDF projects in Kacheliba and thence provides the model background for this study. Lindblom (1959) argued that Model addresses how public policy is formed. Long run political opinions needs the thought of problems within the gift that have consequences for inhabitants of future years, either as a result of current problems and choices can extend into coming decades or as a result of new policy challenges are often fairly anticipated. Political opinions is simply one a part of the whole policy method. It describes the duties and arrangements of bureaus and departments. Additionally it considers constitutional provisions, body and customary law, and judicial choices. According to Ghanbari (2014), World Health Organization determined that it focuses on formal arrangements like political orientation government reorganizations, presidential commission among others. Historically politics has studied government establishments Congress, presidency, courts, political parties, etc. that magisterially confirm, implement, and enforce public policy. To be precise, a policy isn't a public policy till it's adopted, enforced and enforced by some governmental establishment. Government lends legitimacy to policies, they're then legal; Government extends policies universally to hide all folks in society; Government monopolizes the ability to pressure obedience to policy, or to sanction violators. Ancient studies favored the institutional approach centered on institutional structures, organization, duties and performance, while not investigated their impact on public policy (Addy, 2012).

Women in Development Approach

Women in development (WID) approach were among one amongst the earliest approaches on gender equality and is linked to the variable of gender awareness to produce an evidence on how the body will use gender awareness to realize a competitive advantage to boost the performance. This theory centered completely on the livelihoods and development of

girls in totality (Jacquette, 1982). The ladies in development approach showcased weaknesses that were known by trendy students within the Nineteen Eighties. World Health Organization argued that there was got to embody men within the gender discussion since the ladies in development approach entirely centered on women whereas men were left isolated (Nyachieng'a, 2012). The ladies in development approach demonstrate the requirement to embrace men within the realization of girls' potential contribution to development within the society thence reviewing the roles and responsibilities of women within the society. The ladies in development approach seek to grasp the roles of girls within the society whereas exploring environmental social and cultural factors that influence the decision-making capability of girls within the society (Mbogori, 2014).

The woman in development theory has relevancy for this study since it illustrates a number of the factors that influence gender mainstreaming. The approach reiterates on the importance of each men and women in realizing property development and recognizing women as integral members of the society. Ingle Hart & writer (2003) study on gender difference highlighted factors that hinder ladies from access to equal opportunities as men within the society. The factors are; institutional style and policy, social cultural factors and egalitarian gender attitudes that's essential to development and can be necessary to the present study. This theory provides insight on factors that influence gender mainstreaming that are: gender policies, cultural practices, resource mobilization and gender awareness. Therefore, the research worker can study the influence of gender mainstreaming on performance of CDF comes.

Butler's Gender Relations Theory

This theory is joined to the variable quantity of gender cultural practices to produce evidence on how the body will use cultural practices to boost the performance. In line with this theory all gender activities sometimes are unit set in terms of cultural norms by the society. During this case, there exist ways through which the society dictates the roles of men and ladies (Butler, 1998). Susan (2016) conquers with Butler's argument by stating that the society plays a basic role in gender mainstreaming. The society plays a task of assignment of roles to each men and ladies. This suggests that men and ladies have clear roles that they play in development activities. For Mukuka (2013) sexes that subscribe to the thought of social relations directly influences gender relationships. The tip results of this read is that gender is delineated as a human process and not as non-equals relationship. The result of this ideology is with relevancy result in the vital areas of the society such as: faith, politics and division of labor. In alternative cases, men area unit aforementioned by World Health Organization sometimes outline social norms that stipulates the role of girls within the society. This means that men area unit possible to favor themselves by selecting sensible roles likes technological careers whereas assign to ladies reduced roles Nekesa (2016). The assorted studies administered by students on gender mainstreaming affirm that almost all societies have clear roles for ladies and men. Thus this theory has relevancy during this study as a result it explains how cultural practices influence gender mainstreaming and the way that have an effect on the performance of development projects like CDF projects. This theory can facilitate the research worker to review factors that will directly influence the connection between gender mainstreaming and performance of CDF projects.

The resource-based price (RBV)

This theory was developed by Calderia and Ward (2009) and is joined to the variable quantity of gender mainstreaming resources to produce evidence on how the body will use gender mainstreaming to realize a competitive advantage to boost the performance. This theory explains that the organization will solely gain a competitive advantage if it has resources such as: "physical and, human or structural resources" (Parker and Castleman, 2009). The strength of this theory lies in its rationalization of the advantage a corporation will have if it's some capabilities like tangible and intangible resources. For Calderia and Ward (2009) the firm will solely adopt a replacement technology if it possesses each tangible and intangible resource. The speculation more has relevancy as a result of it permits the managers to grasp the structure competencies. This is often vital in the organization in designing part of the CDF projects (Parker and Castelman, 2009). However Duan et al. (2002) were skeptical concerning this model and its relevancy. They noted that this theory will solely be applicable in massive organizations. Parker and Castleman (2009) additionally critiqued this theory by contestation that the speculation didn't sufficiently account for external factors.

Conceptual framework

Conceptual framework consists of independent variable and dependent variable. The independent variables are gender policy, cultural practices and gender mainstreaming resources and gender awareness while the dependent variable is performance of CDF projects as show in figure 2.1 below.

Figure 2.1 Conceptual Framework

Review of Variables

Influence of gender policy on the performance of CDF project

According to the United Nations (1997) gender policy was adopted by the Fourth World Conference on Women in 1995 with an aim of making sure the governments have incorporated gender issues into the implementation, design, and monitoring all the programs and policies with regard to gender mainstreaming perspectives. In addition, the United Nations and Governments were to ensure men and women participate effectively in the activities and programs that aim at promoting gender perspectives prior to any decision on identified goals, resource allocation and in identification of strategies.

In addition, the Beijing Platform for Action was very critical in recognizing the principal institutional response in advancing women agenda and in formulating of national machineries where women can be trained and equipped with skills and get appropriate support from the government. The platform lays down the necessary actions that are crucial in integration of the gender issues in areas such as public policies, legislation, projects and programs as well as the role of the national machineries in addressing gender perspectives (United Nations, 1997).

Mitchell (2004) noted that to implement and facilitate policies related to gender equality, the government should develop appropriate methodologies and strategies. The government should also coordinate and cooperate with other partners to

ensure gender mainstreaming issues are addressed during the policy making process at all levels. The commonwealth Secretariat, 1999) cautioned that without formal policies especially at all levels of the national strategy, and the national action plan that aims at advancing women in the local and at sectoral action plans.

Arenas and Lentisco (2017) conducted a study in Australia, from the study, gender policies and organizational techniques were identified to have a fundamental impact on implementation of gender mainstreaming programs. According to CCGD (2016) policies should be used in determining every single step that can lead to intended impact. In that sense, focus should be on ensuring all the exercises are conducted within the established limitations. To achieve this goal, there must be strategies and policies formulated based on real life and daily tasks of the organization (Mwendwa et al, 2019). The study carried out by Mwendwa et al. (2019) on influence of gender mainstreaming on implementation of development projects established that gender policy plays critical role in gender mainstreaming at the organizational level. Accordingly, the gender policy is highly needed during the setting of targets and in gender empowerment plans. The gender policy ensures there is gender balance and gender defined duties in the organization. According to CCGD (2017) organizational systems play a critical role in shaping the national impact on gender mainstreaming. Some of the organizational requirements with regard to gender mainstreaming include the organizations vision, goals, objectives and needs.

According to Blair (2000), implementation of the gender policies at different levels of the government has not been successful because of several reasons linked to administration and political systems. He noted that gender policy cannot be properly implemented if there is tension between the local government and the central government with regard to planned objectives and the informal development efforts that are being made at the local level. This leads to women not to be considered appropriately in the decision making of such development projects.

A study undertaken by Chadha, (2005) established that Government policies with regard to gender policy in development projects is of critical importance in shaping the direction of involvement by any kind of grassroots levels. Additionally, Chadha (2005) stated that in such cases where there is tension between the policy of the state and development projects, there is tendency of political power directing direction of development projects or attempts to co-opt such projects for party political reasons. It can therefore be seen that nature of political environment in a particular state will influence participation of local groups.

An observation was made by Hague (2009) on the influence of government on participation in development projects in regard to existing legal system. In his study, Hague notes that existing legal system within a country can seriously frustrate efforts to promote participation in development functions. Two ways in which he identified this would happen was through; legal system with an inherent bias both in the way it is conducted in which it maintains status quo, on other hand many urban youths being unaware of their legal rights and of the services legally available to them. This he explains was largely contributed by the fact that many legal systems do not overly seek to impact this information to slum people who largely remain ignorant and excluded from effect of law which is supposed to benefit them. In other instances, Blair (2000) notes that legal systems acts as direct constraint on involvement in development activities. This is particularly the case in terms of legislation which governs the rights of legal association of different categories of workers.

Influence of cultural practices on performance of CDF projects

According to United Nations (2017) women are sidelined from participating in development projects due to various reasons. For instance, conventions and social practices are cited as the major hindrances to women participation in development projects because they segregate and sideline them from the overall population. The 1975 principal meeting that was held in Mexico noted that sidelining women that was being experienced in most parts of the world such as Asia, Africa, and Latin America results into women being confined to jobs such as homecare, cooking, dealing with children and getting water. This pushes women away from fundamental monetary development (UN Women, 2015). For World Bank (2018) social practices and conventions are to be blamed for women's low participation in development. The report noted that some social practices and conventions are not safe for women especially young ladies. These challenges make women vulnerable to gender based violence which contributes to weak morale for women to participate in development projects as their male counterparts (OECD, 2019).

The study conducted in Ethiopia by Klasen and Francesca (2018) established that social practices such as poor view of women jobs in the general public, early marriage and poor practices such as FGM contribute to poor interest of women participation in development projects in Ethiopia. Kipuri and Ridgewell (2018) noted that culture is the major cause of

women's poor participation in development projects such as CDF projects. Pastoralist's cultural practices are said to be prohibitive for women's active participation in development activities because they only advocate for women to act as housewives who are supposed to take care of children and do other household chores especially in North Eastern Part of Kenya.

Another study conducted among the Maasai community living both in Tanzania and Kenya by Michael (2017) revealed that women are involved in various projects at the household level such as rising of children and building houses. However, in real implementation of development projects such as the CDF projects, they are prohibited from participation based on cultural restrictions. This prohibition is blamed for early-marriages and school dropouts among women in the Maasai community. The result of such cultures is that it leads to women taking passive roles especially in decision making forums on fundamental issues that affect their lives.

Ngunjiri (2017) conducted a study in Tana River and Oroma on factors that hinder women from participating in development. From his study, social works were identified as the major obstructs to women participation in peaceful networks and in development activities. Some of the practices cited include: early constrained relationship, FGM, Widows legacy, early pregnancy among others.

The study carried out in Pakistani on socio-cultural factors influencing the economic empowerment of women in Pakistan: a situation analysis indicated that the current legal right of women to have access to property is not operational. Islamic and other post-independence laws appear to support women's access to resources, but dominant male counterparts need to implement this (Choudhry et al 2019).

Another study by Roy et al (2017) in Bangladesh showed that women are left out from generating income activities, leading them to dependent on their male counterparts. Prevailing cultural practices, coupled with inadequate education and inadequate skills for marketing and lack of access to job opportunities result into women's inability to contribute to their economic wellbeing and to participate in decision making. Cultural practices in Bangladesh prevent women from participating in economic development but rather restrict women to domestic life making them to spend most of their time doing housework (Roy, Jannat& Khan, 2017).

Influence of availability of gender mainstreaming Resources on performance of CDF projects

The ability of both men and women to participate in development depends in some ways on the availability of resources. However, the prevailing evidence shows that human resources needed to facilitate women participation in development activities are not sufficient (Gumbo and Foster, 2005).

According to Kisiang'ani (2017) gender mainstreaming can be achieved when resources are allocated resources to facilitate gender mainstreaming activities. This shows that professionals in the development projects should ensure the availability of resources that is needed to promote gender mainstreaming during the undertaking development projects (Gumbo & Robinson, 2004). In all of these cases, rural women are the most affected. Most of the poor and marginalized women live in rural areas where they are mainly engaged in agriculture (Anon, 1995). But their contribution to food security and family well-being is neither appreciated nor incorporated as a development strategy (Murshid and Yasmeeen, 2004). For Acharya, 2003), the lack of access and control over productive resources results in a limitation of the equal participation of women in economic activities, preventing them from accessing income and the economic strengthening of the home.

Studies from around the world indicate that women's access to business increases women's overall status and empowers them. The study conducted (Carr et al. (1996) in Asia established that women's emancipation is the main cause of women's economic development. On the other hand, the study by Rahman et al. (2016) concluded that several men adults within the family influence women's decision-making as to whether or not to work in the fields.

In Kenya, women face challenges similar to those faced by other women globally. For example, women continue to be under-represented in decision-making at all levels and have less access to land ownership, education and job opportunities (USAID, 2019).

Influence of gender awareness on performance of CDF projects

According to Ayyagari, Beck and Demirguc-kunt (2017) gender awareness refers to the state of being mindfulness of gender as a fundamental aspect in gender mainstreaming. This comprise of collecting accurate information concerning to women

in a given society. The information should capture the status of women in social and monetary settings and must be able to show what can be done. To achieve this, preparation education both formally and casually is necessary. Training is paramount in this case, because it equips women with skills and knowledge to engage effectively in the general public (World Bank, 2018).

The study by the Asian Development Bank (2017) in Sri-Lanka indicated that women were not very well educated in various policies developed by the bank with regard to financing of projects being implemented in Sri-Lanka. According to AsDB (2017) the absence of women in development projects leads to poor cooperation especially in development projects being financed by the bank in areas such as agribusiness, education, wellbeing among many others.

Awareness creation on the presence of development projects and the necessity of women involvement in such projects could be a crucial aspect in promoting the participation in development projects. In this study, awareness will be scrutinized in the context of interpersonal communication among the women and how this has affected participation in development projects. A study carried out by Samad, (2002) indicated that slum dwellers do not maximize the use of services provided through the development projects because of lack of skills and knowledge concerning the available services. This creates a challenge with regard to communication strategy that the development projects implementing organization can adopt in such areas as slums to create awareness of the project being implemented.

Performance of CDF projects

According to Act of Parliament CDF Act 2003 amended in (2007), Constituency Development Fund was established to address inequality and poverty across the country. This was to be achieved through setting aside a specific amount of the Government revenue to address social and economic needs that affect the community at the grassroots level. According to the act, the fund was to be managed by the Constituency Development Fund Board (CDFB).

The Fund has registered great success through shifting the role of project identification, planning and implementation from line ministries to communities, hence encouraging local initiative that results in a sense of ownership, transparency and accountability. The program has also encouraged the creation of employment at local levels through awarding contracts to local artisans and sourcing materials from local entrepreneurs. Through CDF, the general condition of social infrastructure has improved in many parts of the country, and school dropout rate has reduced through CDF contribution in the expansion of learning facilities and provision of a bursary to needy students. In January 2013, Parliament enacted CDF Act, 2013, hence effectively repealing CDF Act 2003 as amended in 2007 (CDF Press Statement, 2013). The enactment of CDF Act 2013 was mainly aimed to ensure that the law governing CDF is aligned to the Constitution of Kenya 2010, particularly in compliance with the principle of transparency, accountability, separation of powers and participation of the people. The new law was also aimed to align the operations of the Fund to the new devolved government structure.

The Citizens participate in open public forums convened by the area MP at ward level to elect five persons from whom CDFC members shall be appointed by the MP in consultation with the officer of the Board and the Sub-county Administrator. The area Member of Parliament forwards the names of persons elected to the office of the Board at the constituency and from which members of the CDFC shall be appointed in consultation with the Officer of the Board and the Sub-county Administrator for the Constituency. The MP is also an Ex-officio member of the CDFC and Member of the County Project Committee (CDF Act, 2013).

Constituencies Development Fund Board (CDFB) is a Board that considers project proposals submitted from various constituencies in accordance with the Act, approve for funding those project proposals that are consistent with the Act and send funds to the respective constituency Fund Accounts with respect to the approved projects. The Board also ensures timely and efficient disbursement of funds to every constituency, efficient management of the Fund and to receive and discuss annual reports and returns from the Constituencies. It also ensures compilation of proper records, returns, and reports from the constituencies, receives and addresses complaints and disputes and takes appropriate action. The committee submits a report to the National Assembly Select Committee on monthly basis. The County Projects Committee (CPC) receives and discusses project lists from various constituencies in the County for the purpose of aligning the projects with County's Development Plans and Policies and ensures that no duplication of projects occurs.

Constituency Development Fund Committee (CDFC) deliberates on all project proposals from all wards in the constituency and any other projects which it considers beneficial to the constituency, consult with the relevant government departments to ensure that the cost estimates for the projects are realistic, rank project proposals in order of priority and ensures that projects proposed for funding comply with the Act.

Critiques of the Existing Literature

This study reviewed several literatures related to gender mainstreaming and the effect that it has on performance of CDF projects. The literature noted that gender policy is very necessary in ensuring gender issues are addressed. However, the study failed to show what can be done if the gender policy can be there but the management of the constituency ignored to implement it. The study literature further revealed that patriarchy has a possibility of affecting the performance of development project. The literature cited several countries where culture has allowed men to dominate in all spheres of life. Though this is true in some ways but the literature reviewed failed to show the level of education of those men and some other factors that make them to dominate in development projects. The reviewed literature revealed that the availability of resources to promote gender mainstreaming programs is a necessary prerequisite. The study, however, failed to show how resources promote gender mainstreaming issues for CDF projects. This means the study show how resources for gender mainstreaming programs are necessary at the constituency.

Finally the literature reviewed revealed that the training on gender mainstreaming is very vital in promoting gender mainstreaming. The reviewed literature failed to show how the gender mainstreaming have to be conducted, and how to identify the participants for such trainings whether the community members can participate in such trainings or it is only the CDF officials.

Research Gap

Many authors have elaborate their view on global and regional context while neglecting the local examples like some local regions in Kenya including the CDF of Kacheliba constituency which gives a clear understanding about influence of gender mainstreaming on performance of CDF projects in Kenya. Therefore, this study will concentrate mainly on factors influencing gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects: a case of Kacheliba Constituency. It is becoming a major problem in understanding the gender mainstreaming issues in development projects especially in the local level. This study will help to fill the gap by analyzing the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects.

Summary

The chapter examined and discussed the literature that is related to the study. It also included theoretical framework, conceptual framework, review of variables, critiques of existing literature and research gap.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Introduction

This chapter presents aspects of the research methodology used in the study .Description of the research design that was used, the targeted population, sampling design, data collection instruments and procedures, and the techniques on how the data was analyzed.

Research Design

Research design could be a framework that shows how knowledge is collected and analyzed (Bryman and Bell, 2011). It conjointly shades light-weight on how knowledge is collected analyzed and measured. In supporting this, there are many analysis styles which can be utilized in the study such as: survey, reciprocity, descriptive and exploratory analysis style (Kothari, 2003). This study utilized survey analysis style to acquire knowledge from the population under examination to change the man of science create a determination of the population standing on one or additional variables (Silva, 2013). Survey style is acceptable as a result of this study because it involves the massive population that's not homogenous geographically. This style is acceptable because it allows the man of science to gather knowledge without favoritism by using either qualitative or quantitative analysis approaches. Qualitative approaches allows assortment of information style of words instead of numbers. It provides verbal descriptions instead of numerical. This finding is in line with Anderson (2013) & Hughes (2013), United Nations agency established that qualitative strategies will be accustomed to gain additional information thorough that and is also tough to be sent quantitatively.

On the other hand, Quantitative approach strives for exactness and it focuses on things which can be counted placed into planned classes and subjected to applied mathematics analysis (Taylor, 2014). This can be in line with the findings of Zhu et al. (2013) who ascertained that the employment of those two approaches reinforces one another. The analysis can use

this approach as a result of the info which was collected from the most form were going to be quantitative and can be analyzed using unbiased statistics. Qualitative on the opposite hand involve interpretation of phenomena while not reckoning on numerical activity or applied mathematics strategies (Styles et al., 2012). As noted in Anderson (2013), mixed analysis is approach that mixes or associates each qualitative and quantitative analysis methods: allows mutual confirmation of one another via the employment of multiple sources of collection knowledge, contextualizes the analysis by providing richer details and initiates new lines of thinking through attention and surprises, turning ideas around and providing contemporary insights. It serves to provide analysis of descriptive development or characteristics related to a theme population, estimates of proportions of population that have these characteristics and discovery of associations among totally different variables (Creswell, 2014).

Target Population

According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) population refers to a full cluster of objects and individuals that have shared evident characteristics. Kothari (2004) conjointly agree that population is all objects in any field of universe or inquiry. The target population on the opposite hand refers to the complete set of events, folks or things of interest that investigator needs to be investigated (Sekaran&Bougie, 2010). During this study, the population of the study was two hundred participants comprising of CDF committee of Kacheliba constituency, community members, Project leaders, and project committee members from the twenty five CDF projects.

Table 3.1: Target population

Section	Target Population
CDF committee members	14
Project leaders	30
Project committee members	56
Community members	100
Total	200

Sample size and sampling procedure

Kothari (2012) noted that sampling is method of finding information bearing on whole population by observing a part of it. This study used purposive sampling. In purposive sampling, the researcher picks the respondents depending on the goal or the aim that he/she needs to accomplish. Therefore, the study sampled one hundred members drawn from the CDF committee, project leaders, project committee members, and community members drawn from twenty five CDF projects.

Sampling frame

Mugenda and Mugenda (2003) speak of sampling as the list of cases from which a sample may be derived. The residents of Kacheliba and CDF committee members, project leaders, and project committee members established the sampling frame, additionally called the supply list from that the samples was drawn. This study used simple random sampling method after the adopted of the Yamane formula in arriving at the sample size for the study as computed and presented in table 3.1 below;

$$n = \frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$$

Where

n sample size

N the population size

e the level of precision

$$n = \frac{200}{1 + 200(0.05)^2} = 398 \text{ Respondents}$$

Research Instruments

Regarding the methodology, primary and secondary sources were used to collect knowledge from the sphere. Primary knowledge sources involved getting info through structured questionnaires and semi-structured questionnaires that may be administered to respondents directly in Kacheliba Constituency. Per Davidson et al., (2002) the utilization of primary knowledge assortment sources offers considerable blessings that enable the man of science to get knowledge directly. It additionally permits the researcher to style their own analysis queries and explore a specific topic of interest while not looking forward to secondary sources. The utilization of structured and semi-structured questionnaires is especially most popular, because it provides respondents enough time to mirror on the queries and supply credible, non-partial answers. However, an obstacle of exploitation questionnaires for this explicit analysis is that it's pricey because it involves plenty of travel, one thing which will greatly inflate the value of conducting all the analysis (Sybil Lewis, 2015).

The study also involved the implementation of secondary sources of information assortment, like document review. The choice of secondary analysis as a technique is even for many reasons. First, secondary analysis makes it easier for the man of science to gather the required knowledge. Since the sources square measure without delay obtainable on the web, it's easier for the man of science to gather the obtainable knowledge by accessing them on the web. The second reason that justifies the utilization of secondary knowledge is that it's cheaper than the applying of primary knowledge. This is because of the understanding that knowledge can be simply accessed from the web compared to primary analysis, wherever it's necessary to succeed in the sphere for knowledge assortment. The third reason is that secondary analysis helps to effectively address analysis queries because of the varied findings which were compared. Comparison completely different points of read of the investigation can modify the understanding of the objectives of the investigation. However, whereas operating with secondary analysis, the investigator ought to take care with the conflicting results given by alternative investigators. It's going to be inappropriate to answer analysis queries if the man of science doesn't listen to gaps in secondary analysis. To avoid compromising the standard of the analysis, the man of science ought to concentrate on the standard of the various studies employed in his analysis. This implies that the man researcher should apply for peer - reviewed articles get the answers to question (s) of analysis and address the objectives developed in analysis (Cook, 1999).

Data collection Procedure

Data collection was conducted by a self-completion questionnaire administered by researcher with the help of research assistants. Each subject was given verbal instructions and asked to anonymously complete the questionnaire for immediate collection. The respondents were informed on the purpose of the study to minimize any biases in data collection procedures. After sampling the relevant respondents, sensitization of the intended study for the entire exercise was carried out. The questionnaires were then distributed to the sampled respondents for the data collection exercise. Besides, the respondents were granted adequate time and questionnaires picked up the following day as agreed with them. Considering that the questions are structured in English and that not all the respondents are well versed with the language, research assistants helped in translating and explaining the questions but ensured that they are not imposing their views on the respondents.

Pilot test

Pilot testing is an important component of the data collection process. A pilot test on a selected sample of respondents was conducted in Kacheliba Constituency and it involved 39 respondents who represent 10 percent of the sample size. This aided in ascertaining the validity and reliability of the questionnaire before being administered to the target population. It is usually a small-scale trial run of all the procedures planned for use in the main study. In particular, pilot testing of an instrument administered for research purposes, says a questionnaire, is the standard in social sciences and was employed in the study once a questionnaire were finalized and tried out in the field (Mugenda & Mugenda, 2003). One form of pilot testing is pre-testing, which may be repeated several times to refine the questions, the instrument or procedures (Cooper & Schindler, 2003). Benefits of pre-testing include an opportunity to test the hypothesis, allowance for checking statistical and analytical procedures, a chance to reduce problems and mistakes in the study and the reduction of costs incurred by inaccurate instruments (Isaac & Michael, 1995). According to Cooper and Schindler (2006) and Mugenda & Mugenda (2003) a sample of at least 10% of the population is usually acceptable in a pilot study. Therefore, to pre-test the research instrument a sample of 39 respondents, who are part of the target population and not the sample size, were used.

Pilot testing provided an opportunity to detect and remedy any potential problems with the research instrument (questionnaire), including questions respondents do not understand; ambiguous questions; questions that combine two or more issues in a single question; questions that make respondents uncomfortable. The critical issues of validity and reliability of the measuring instrument are addressed including the design of questions, the structure of the questionnaire and the diligence of pilot testing. To increase validity and reliability, pilot study was conducted to pre-test the questionnaire.

Validity

Validity is the ability of an instrument to measure what it is designed to measure. It is the correctness or credibility of a description, conclusion, explanation, interpretation, or other sorts of account (Kumar, 2005). According to Kumar (2005), there are two approaches to establishing the validity of a research instrument: logic and statistical evidence. Validity was established by a logical link between questions and the objectives (Kumar, 2005). There are three dimensions from which validity can be examined. These include, content, construct, and criterion validity (Orotho, 2009). Content validity was ensured by designing instrument according to the study variables and their respective indicators of measurement; construct validity was maintained through restricting the questions to the conceptualizations of the variables and ensuring that the indicators of a particular variable fall within the same construct.

Reliability

Reliability is an assessment of the degree of consistency between multiple measurements of a variable (Hair et al, 2010). Reliability is a measure of the degree to which a research instrument yields consistent results or data after repeated trials (Mugenda&Mugenda, 2003). Reliability relates to the consistency of the data collected and degree of accuracy in the measurements made using a research instrument. The greater the ability of the instrument to produce consistent results, again and again, or rather the repeatability of the measure, the greater is its reliability. An item analysis will be conducted to determine internal consistency and reliability of each individual item as well as each sub-scale of the data collection instrument in accordance with Kumar (2005). Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient α was used or the internal reliability test. The coefficient normally ranges between 0 and 1 although actually no lower limits exist. The closer α is to 1.0 the greater the internal consistency of the items in the scale. The size of α was determined by both the number of items in the scale and the mean inter-item correlations.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 was used for data analysis. In this, all the questionnaires and items in the questionnaire were coded to facilitate data entry after being referenced. Subsequently data cleaning which involved checking for errors in descriptive statistics such as frequencies, entry, percentages, standard deviation and mean score was projected for all the quantitative variables and information presented in form of tables. Multiple regression analysis was conducted to establish inferential data. Multiple regression analysis was used to find the associations between the dependent and independent variables. Multiple regressions were preferred because it is the method that utilizes two or more independent variables to make a prediction about a dependent variable. Because there are three independent variables in this study the multiple regression models generally assumed the following equation;

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \beta_3 X_3 + \beta_4 X_4 + \epsilon$$

Where: Y= performance of CDF projects

β_0 =constant; $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 = regression coefficients

X_1 =gender policy

X_2 = Cultural practices

X_3 =gender mainstreaming resources

X_4 = Gender awareness

ϵ =Error Term

4. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Introduction

This chapter presents the study findings on the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects in Kacheliba constituency, West Pokot County, Kenya.

Response Rate

In this study, a total of three hundred and ninety eight (398) questionnaires were distributed in Kacheliba constituency, West Pokot County. Out of the 398 questionnaires that were distributed, 335 were satisfactorily filled, 23 were not satisfactorily completed and 40 were unreturned for analysis. The three hundred and thirty five (335) questionnaires that were satisfactorily filled and returned for analysis yielded a return rate of 84.17 percent. This questionnaire return rate was very reliable response rate to enable generalizations of the study findings. This agrees with Zikmund et al., (2010) who noted that a response rate of 70 percent and above is a reliable response rate.

Table 4.1: Response Rate

Questionnaire Response	Number	Percentage
Satisfactorily Filled	335	84.17
Not Satisfactorily Filled	23	5.78
Unreturned	40	10.05
Total	398	100

Pilot test results

According to Zikmund (2003) a pilot test is a small-scale study piloted to formulate for the study or research (2003). A pilot study is conducted to test the reliability and validity of the data collection instrument before the actual data collection is done. In line with this, the research instrument was pretested in one local that was not included in the actual data collection. Connelly (2008) stated that a good study sample for a pilot study should be at least 10% of the projected sample. Thus, the sample size for the pilot study comprised of 39 respondents.

Pilot Study Response Rate

The data for questionnaire distribution was analyzed and presented in Table 4.2 below;

Table 4.2: Pilot test Response Rate

Questionnaire Response	Number	Percentage
Satisfactorily Filled	29	74.36
Not Satisfactorily Filled	8	20.51
Unreturned	2	5.13
Total	39	100

Thirty nine (39) questionnaires were distributed to targeted respondents in Kacheliba Constituency, West Pokot County involving respondents that did not take part in the actual study. Out of the total number of questionnaires distributed, twenty nine (29) questionnaires were satisfactorily filled and returned, eight (8) was incomplete and therefore considered not satisfactory for the purpose of the study, while two of the questionnaire was not returned at all. This represented a response rate of 74.36% which was considered convenient and hence acceptable for data analysis. According to Mugenda and Mugenda (2013), a response rate above 70% is well recommended for research purposes.

Reliability of Research Instruments

Reliability analysis refers to a measure the consistency of the research instrument and hence adopted in ensuring that the research instrument reflects the overall reliability of the study variables (Cohen and Sayang 2010). A Cronbach Alpha Coefficient was used to test internal consistency of the variables and determine how they correlated among themselves (Cronbach, 1951). Cohen and Sayang(2010) stated that the coefficient values range from 0 to 1, and that the most acceptable alpha is 0.70 and above.

Table 4.3: Reliability Analysis

Variables	Cronbach alpha	Comment
Gender policy	.736	Acceptable
Cultural practices	.794	Acceptable
Gender mainstreaming resources	.787	Acceptable
Gender awareness	.824	Acceptable
Performance of CDF projects	.845	Accepted

The findings indicated that the independent variables; gender policy, had a coefficient of 0.736; cultural practices had a coefficient of 0.794, gender mainstreaming resources had a coefficient of 0.787, and gender awareness had a coefficient .824, while the dependent variable, performance of CDF projects had a coefficient of 0.845. All constructs depicted that the values of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient are above the suggested value of 0.7 thus the study was reliable (Calmorin, 2017). Based on the reliability test, it was concluded that the scale used in this study was reliable to capture the constructs.

Validity of Research Instruments

Kothari (2014) stated that validity of a research instrument measures the degree to which results obtained from the data analysis represent what is actually being studied. Creswell (2013) indicated that Validity measures the extent to which the questions in the research instrument relate to the expected accuracy and the degree to which data analysis results obtained represents the phenomenon under study and whether it's a true reflection of the variables. The research instruments were checked and perfected by the supervisor who is an expert in research work to ensure the research instrument meets the required standards.

Demographic Data

Age of the respondents

In this study, 26.27 percent of the respondents were of the age bracket between 21-30 years, 47.16 percent of the respondents were between 31-40 years, 23.58 percent were between 41-50 years and 2.99 percent were over 50 years of age. The results are summarized in table 4.3 below.

Table 4.4: Respondents Age

Age bracket (Years)	Frequency	Percent
21-30	88	26.27
31-40	158	47.16
41-50	79	23.58
51 and above	10	2.99
TOTAL	335	100

Academic qualifications

The respondents were asked to indicate their level of education. From the results obtained, the study indicated that 39.77 percent of the respondents had certificates, 38.64 percent were diploma holders, 18.18 percent had attained a bachelor's degree level of education, and 3.41 percent were master's degree holders, while none of the respondents had attained philosophical doctorate level of education.

Presentation of Findings

Influence of gender policy on performance of CDF projects

a. Are you familiar with gender mainstreaming policies? Briefly explain.

The respondents were asked to indicate whether they are familiar with gender mainstreaming policies. The results obtained showed that 50.75 percent of the respondents are familiar with gender policy. They explained that the CDF committee has educated them on gender mainstreaming policies but they feel the knowledge they have so far is not adequate particularly in understanding gender policy. On the other hand, 49.25 pointed out that they are not familiar about gender policy and that nobody has told them anything about it.

b. Have you ever attended any gender mainstreaming policy development sessions?

The respondents were further asked to indicate whether they have ever attended any gender mainstreaming policy development sessions? The study established that 67.83 have never attended any gender mainstreaming gender policy. The respondents explained that such forums are attended by few elites and other residents are always overlooked. They also pointed out that most of those policies are developed in secret without the awareness of the residents. The 31.17 percent who indicated that they have attended gender mainstreaming policy development sessions revealed that they are basically the opinion leaders in their respective communities that is why they have managed to attend such sessions.

c. The likert scale results

The first objective of this study was to examine the influence of gender policy on performance of CDF projects. In determining this objective, the respondents were requested to respond to several statements regarding gender policy. The findings were presented in a five point Likerts scale where SA=strongly agree, A=agree, N=No idea, D=disagree, SD=strongly disagree and T=total.

First, the respondents were asked whether the policies that address gender mainstreaming related issues can affect the performance of CDF projects. The distribution of findings showed that 42.5 percent of the respondents strongly agreed, 40 percent of them agreed, 13.75 percent of the respondents had no idea, 2.25 percent disagreed while 1.25 percent of them strongly disagreed. These findings indicated that the policies that address gender mainstreaming related issues affect the performance of CDF projects. The respondents were also asked whether in cases where gender mainstreaming is not well articulated, the performance of the project is likely to be affected. The distribution of the responses indicated that 25 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 58.75 percent of them agreed, and 11.25 percent of them were neutral, 1.25 percent of them disagreed while 1.25 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. The findings show that in cases where gender mainstreaming is not well articulated, the performance of the project is likely to be affected. In addition, the respondents were also asked whether gaps in the gender mainstreaming issues are always addressed before the CDF project commences. The distribution of the responses indicated that 12.5 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 17.5 percent of them agreed, and 1.25 percent of them were had no idea, 32.5 percent of them disagreed while 36.25 percent of them strongly disagreed to the statement. These findings indicated that gaps in the gender mainstreaming issues are always not addressed before the CDF projects commence.

The respondents were asked whether there is proper monitoring and evaluation of gender mainstreaming to ensure they are properly implemented. The distribution of the responses indicated that 20 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 32.5 percent of them agreed, 16.25 percent of them were neutral while 21.25 percent and 10 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These show that there is proper monitoring and evaluation of gender mainstreaming to ensure they are properly implemented.

Finally, the respondents were asked whether there is a robust gender mainstreaming policies and programs in CDF projects. The distribution of the responses indicated that 12.5 percent strongly agreed to the statement, 17.5 percent of them agreed, 1.25 percent of them were neutral while 36.7 percent and 32.5 percent of them disagreed strongly and disagreed to the statement respectively. These show that there are no robust gender mainstreaming policies and programs in the CDF projects.

Table 4.5: Influence of gender policy on performance of CDF projects

Statements		SA	A	N	D	SD	T
The policies that address gender mainstreaming related issues can affect the performance of CDF projects.	%	42.5	40.0	13.75	2.5	1.25	100
In cases where gender mainstreaming is not well articulated, the performance of the project is likely to be affected.	%	28.0	58.7	11.25	1.25	1.25	100
gaps in the gender mainstreaming issues are always addressed before the CDF project commences	%	12.5	17.5	1.25	32.5	36.25	100

There is proper monitoring and evaluation of gender mainstreaming to ensure they are properly implemented % 20.0 16.25 21.25 16.25 10 100

In all the departments of the organization, there is a robust gender mainstreaming policies and programs in CDF projects % 12.5 17.5 1.25 36.7 32.5 100

Table 4.6: Model summary

Model	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Estimation error
One	.805	0.649	.000

a. Predictors: (constant), gender policy, Cultural practices, gender mainstreaming resources, and gender awareness

b. Dependent variable: performance of CDF projects

ANOVA model

The study results in ANOVA table 4.7 indicated that the coefficient of determination discussed above was significant as evidence of an F ratio of 14.692 with a p-value of 0.000 < 0.05 (significance level). Therefore, the model was adapted to predict the performance of CDF projects using gender policy, cultural practices, gender mainstreaming resources, and gender awareness.

Table 4.7: ANOVA

Template	Sum of squares	Df	Medium square	F.	Sig
Regression	59.912	4	59.912	14.692	.05 ^b
1 Residue	1361.945	335	4.078		
Total	1421.857	339			

Test of hypotheses

Hypothesis one

Ho1: Gender policy do not have a statistically significant effect on the performance of CDF projects

The first hypothesis of the study stated that there is a significant relationship between gender policy and the performance of CDF projects. The results of Table 4.28 showed that gender policy had estimation coefficients that were significant based on $\beta_1 = -0.307$ (p-value = 0.000 which is less than $\alpha = 0.05$), so we accept the hypothesis and conclude that there is a significant relationship between gender policy and the performance of CDF projects. This suggests that there is a decrease of up to 0.307 units in the performance of CDF projects for each unit of increase in gender policy. Furthermore, the effect of gender policy is greater than the effect attributed to the error, this is indicated by the value of the test $t = 2.921$.

5. SUMMARY, CONCLUSIONS, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Introduction

This chapter presents a discussion of the findings, conclusions, and recommendations based on the study's objectives.

Summary of results

Influence of gender policy on Performance of CDF projects

The first objective of this study was to examine the influence of gender policy on performance of development projects. In determining this objective, the respondents were requested to respond to several statements regarding gender policy. The study established that policies that address gender mainstreaming related issues affect the performance of CDF projects. The findings further showed that in cases where gender mainstreaming is not well articulated, the performance of the project is likely to be affected. The study also indicated that gaps in the gender mainstreaming issues are always not addressed

before the CDF projects commence. Additionally, the study showed that there is proper monitoring and evaluation of gender mainstreaming to ensure they are properly implemented. Finally, the study revealed that there are no robust gender mainstreaming policies and programs in the CDF projects.

Conclusion

Influence of gender policy on Performance of CDF projects

The study concluded that there is a significant relationship between gender policy and the performance of CDF projects. This suggests that there is a decrease of up to 0.307 units in the performance of development projects for each unit of increase in gender policy. Furthermore, the effect of gender policy is greater than the effect attributed to the error, this is indicated by the value of the test $t = 2.921$.

Recommendations

Based on the results, the study recommended the following:

Influence of gender policy on Performance of CDF projects

The study established that if gender mainstreaming is not well articulated, then the performance of the project is likely to be affected. This study therefore recommends that gender issues should be properly articulated to be implemented.

Further research areas

The study analyzed the influence of gender mainstreaming on the performance of CDF projects in Kenya: a case of Kacheliba Constituency, West Pokot Sub County. The study recommends that another study be conducted on influence of gender mainstreaming in the county governments funded projects in Kenya. Additionally, a replication study must be conducted in another county for there to be sufficient and conclusive results regarding the study.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

First and foremost, I want to give thanks to the Almighty God for the gift of abundance of healthy Life. I would also like to take this opportunity to acknowledge Dr. Nyaberi my supervisor for taking time out of his busy schedule to supervise my research project, they provided me with the insights and guidance during development of this research project despite the prevailing COVID-19 Pandemic challenges.

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